

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' MONOLOGUE SPEECH EXPRESSION SKILLS

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Abstract:

Monologue speech is, as is known, the speech of one person expressing in a more or less detailed form his thoughts, intentions, assessment of events, etc. One of the tasks put forward by the program is teaching monologue speech. The goal of training is to develop monologue speech skills, which are understood as the ability to express one's thoughts orally in a communicatively motivated, logically consistent and coherent manner, sufficiently complete and linguistically correct. This position seems erroneous, since it is this aspect of training that disciplines thinking, teaches one to think logically and, accordingly, construct one's statement in such a way as to convey one's thoughts to the listener.

Key words: thoughts, views, beliefs, actions, preventing action, emotional-evaluative issue

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A monologue is a form of speech when it is built by one person, independently determining the structure, composition and linguistic means. Monologue speech can be reproductive and productive in nature. Reproductive speech is not communicative. Students are given the task of developing students' unprepared productive speech [1]. Monologue speech, like dialogical speech, must be situationally conditioned and, as psychologists say, motivated. The student should have a desire, an intention to communicate something to those listening. The situation is the starting point for the monologue, then it seems to break away from it, forming its own environment - context. Therefore, it is customary to say about a monologue that it is contextual, in contrast to dialogue and polylogue, which are closely dependent on the situation. Due to the contextual nature of monologue speech, special requirements are placed on it: it must be understandable "from itself," i.e. without the help of linguistic means, which often play a large role in situational dialogical speech. As is known, monologue speech has the following communicative functions [2]:

- informative (communication of new information in the form of knowledge about objects and phenomena of the surrounding reality, description of events, actions, states);

- influencing (convincing someone of the correctness of certain thoughts, views, beliefs, actions; inducing action or preventing action);

- emotional-evaluative [3].

For students, the most relevant is the informative function of monologue speech. Each of the above functions of monologue speech is characterized by its

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own linguistic means of expression and special psychological stimuli. It requires the speaker to be able to coherently and consistently express his thoughts, to express them in a clear and distinct form. When mastering monologue speech, the difficulties become significantly more complicated due to the fact that students do not have fluency in the linguistic means that the speaker needs to express thoughts.

Timely mastery of coherent speech is one of the conditions for the formation of a full-fledged personality and preparation for studying. By speech we understand the process of transmitting information. Speech is not only a means of communication, but also a tool of thinking. To formulate speech, 5 components are needed: motive, thought, which is improved in the word, internal speech directed at oneself, semantization, that is, structuring the meaning in grammatically formulated meanings of words [3]. And finally, external speech arises. There are two types of speech expression: oral and written speech.

Oral speech is divided into affective speech (This includes exclamations, speech clichés. In this form there is no motive and stage of thought.), oral dialogical and oral monologue speech. Oral monologue speech has a motive, a thought that arises in the speaker. Monologue as a long-term form of influence on the listener was first identified by L.P. Yakubinsky. S.L. Rubinstein prefers the term “connected speech” to the term “monologue speech” [4]. The author calls semantic relations in speech design speech context, and speech - contextual or coherent. He makes an important conclusion about the need for special training in the basic types of coherent monologue speech.

In search of new forms of work, a creative group was created in our educational institution to test the original methods of T.A. Tkachenko [5]. At this time, we hold consultations in all groups. The material for the study of coherent speech is designed for age based on program requirements and special techniques. T.B. In her program, at the stage of forming coherent monologue speech of students, Filicheva highlights lexical and grammatical work, learning to independently describe objects, learning to tell stories, memorizing poems, learning to retell texts. The main manifestation of speech is the student’s attempt to express a thought.

According to the communicative purpose, the following monologue statements are distinguished [6]:

Monologue-message; monologue-description; monologue-reasoning; monologue-narration; monologue-persuasion. All these statements presuppose the possession of a complex monologue skill of coherent presentation of thoughts, facts, events, manifested, in particular, in the mastery of connecting elements of sentences - adverbs of time, cause-and-effect, adverbs expressing sequence, as well as combining speech patterns known to students in accordance with the goals and the conditions of communication, in particular, the choice of the appropriate word order in sentences, conjunctions and allied words [7]. The influencing function of monologue speech manifests itself especially clearly in the monologue - motivation. Bearing in mind the low, but communicatively sufficient level of mastery of monologue skills, monologue statements are of greatest relevance: description and communication of students about themselves, about their interests, about their hometown, about their family, about everything that can be interesting to an imaginary (or real) native speaker peer. As for teaching monologue speech, planned and systematic training begins in the elementary grades and continues throughout all school years. An educational monologue at the initial stage of training is a simple and

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very short, logically structured statement containing one or more speech samples. Students should be able to speak logically and consistently without prior preparation in accordance with the learning situation, make oral reports on a topic, and convey in their own words the main content of what they listened to or read within the language material. Students are required to be able not only to report facts, but also to express their attitude to what is presented. The volume of the statement is at least 15 phrases, correctly formulated linguistically" [8].

When determining the types of monologue exercises, the following criteria must be taken into account:

1. type of monologue (message, narration, description, reasoning);
2. coherence and logic in the presentation of thoughts and structural and compositional completeness of the statement [9];
3. volume (completeness) of the statement - the degree of disclosure of the topic and the number of sentences;
4. the degree of combination of linguistic (lexical and grammatical) means (i.e. the nature of speech creativity);
5. lexico-grammatical (including syntactic) correctness [10].

Methodologically important are, firstly, the nature of the supports with the help of which exercises are performed when teaching monologue speech, and the purpose of the utterance, secondly. Such supports can be:

- 1) visibility,
- 2) text,
- 3) situation,
- 4) topic (fragment of a topic), problem. This sequence is observed mainly only at the initial stage, then the order of using supports changes; at the middle stage it can be as follows [11]:

- 1) situation,
- 2) visibility,
- 3) text,
- 4) topic; at the senior stage:
 - 1) text,
 - 2) speech situations,
 - 3) visibility (a series of paintings, a movie),
 - 4) topic problem [12].

When forming contextual speech, the main support is written or oral text. To develop the compositional and structural components of monologue skills, an exemplary, "standard" text with a clear structure, consisting of three parts - an introduction (beginning), the main part and a conclusion, can be used. In this case, it is possible to use a special sample scheme for constructing a monologue. Particular difficulties in mastering coherent monologue speech include choosing the order of words in a sentence in a coherent monologue statement and setting the correct logical stress in phrases. As established in the linguistic literature, in a monologue text, the first member of a new sentence often plays the role of a link with the previous context. The function of a connecting element in a sentence, as already mentioned, can be performed by virtually all members of the sentence, especially often this function is performed by all minor members of the sentence - circumstance of time and reason.

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